

Experimental comparison between forward and reverse Vibrant Soundbridge cochlear stimulation

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Various couplers exist for the Vibrant Soundbridge implant to connect the actuator to a middle ear structure. While the surgical indication mainly distinguishes between purely sensorineural hearing loss and mixed hearing loss, and audiological indication ranges are designed accordingly, we believe that the biomechanical distinction between forward and reverse cochlear stimulation is more meaningful. To evaluate this, we apply all common couplers in temporal bone experiments and correct the measurements for adequate comparability.

Material and methods: The study was conducted at two research labs, each with $n = 10$ cadaveric temporal bones. Laser Doppler velocity measurements on the stapes were used for direct comparison between the coupling methods. Therefore, reverse cochlear stimulation requires a correction factor due to pressure loss through a third window. This was calculated by measuring intracochlear pressure differences in the same specimens.

Results: Compared to the stapes LDV measurement, reverse stimulations require a correction factor that continuously decreases in the high frequency range: approximately +22.4 dB between 125–250 Hz, +7.9 dB between 300–800 Hz, and +4.8 dB above 1000 Hz. Taking this into account, there is still a considerable difference between the forward and reverse stimulation methods of 15–22 dB in the frequency range <2000 Hz and approximately 7 dB >2000 Hz to the favor of forward stimulation.

Conclusions: Forward couplings, including direct stapes coupling, are mechanically superior to reverse stimulation. The stapes head coupler performs 7–25 dB better than the round window coupler and similar or even superior to incus couplers.

1. Introduction

The active part of the Vibrant Soundbridge implant (MEDEL, Austria) is an electromagnetic actuator called "floating mass transducer" (FMT) that was originally designed to drive the ossicular chain connected to the long incus process (Dietz et al., 1997). Over the years, several alternative coupling sites have been explored and attachments were developed. Currently, the classification distinguishes between sensorineural hearing loss with an intact ossicular chain (long process

(LP) or short process (SP) coupler (Schraven et al., 2014)) and mixed hearing loss with an impaired ossicular chain. For both situations, separate audiological indication ranges are specified (maximal sensorineural loss of 65 dB HL at 500 Hz and 80–85 dB HL >1 kHz for incus couplers, maximal sensorineural loss of 45 dB HL at 500 Hz and about 65 dB HL >1 kHz for stapes and RW couplers). However, the variations in the anatomy of a diseased middle ear can be large, from a small epitympanic cholesteatoma to an open cavity resulting from multiple previous surgeries and a missing stapes superstructure. Therefore, the

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variety of coupling options is broad: on the stapes superstructure (Stapes head/SH-(Warnholtz et al., 2021), CliP-(Hüttenbrink et al., 2011), Bell-(Huber et al., 2006) coupler), on the stapes footplate (Oval window/OW coupler), or directly on the round window (RW (Colletti et al., 2006), Soft-, Hannover-coupler (HC) (Busch et al., 2017), fat/fascia underlay with no coupler (Arnold et al., 2010)) i.e. as a cochlear reverse stimulation. From a mechanical perspective, the FMT faces a different impedance at each site, which may result in a different cochlear drive (Stieger et al., 2013). In addition, comparative measurements on cadaveric temporal bones are complicated by the fact that an LDV measurement on the stapes or RW represents the intracochlear stimulation fairly well for forward stimulation, whereas in the case of reverse stimulation, the stapes motion must be corrected upwards due to a cochlear pressure loss (Stieger et al., 2013). For RW coupling higher variability in coupling efficiency, an inferior performance, and more revisions compared to other coupling sites are described in literature (Busch et al., 2017; Schraven et al., 2016; Spiegel et al., 2020). In this study we provide structured measurements of all main coupling options pooled from two research laboratories in comparable cadaveric temporal bone experiments. When comparing forward and reverse stimulation, a correction factor calculated from intracochlear pressure measurements is taken into account. Our hypothesis is that, rather than being defined for sensorineural versus mixed hearing loss, the audiological indication range should distinguish between reverse (RW, HC) and forward coupling (all other couplers).

2. Material and methods

Experiments were conducted at two research labs (University Basel Hospital and Hannover Medical School), with ten cadaveric temporal bone specimens at each institution. One research group focused on forward cochlear stimulation in cases of intact or altered middle ears; the other research group compared cochlear reverse stimulation options. Both sets of measurements were referenced to standard SP coupler as the most common clinical application and converted accordingly to ensure adequate comparability. The use of anonymous cadaveric temporal bones was approved by the local ethics committees (EKNZ BASEC 2016-00599, 10495_BO_K_2022). Some data included in this study were published previously (Stauske et al. 2025, Preclinical methods to determine output of the floating mass transducer in forward and reverse stimulation, to be published, (Graf et al., 2023; Graf et al., 2024)).

2.1. Specimens and surgical preparation

Both the forward and the reverse stimulation group used 10 fresh frozen temporal bone specimens harvested <48 h postmortem. Specimens were inspected to assure a morphologically intact tympanic membrane and exclude visual pathologies of the middle ear. A facial recess approach was performed and a free view perpendicular to the round window membrane established. In some cases, pseudo-membranes, adhesions or a part of the mastoid segment of the facial nerve had to be removed. For RW stimulation a part of the bony overhang of the RW niche was dissected. All experiments were conducted with an intact external auditory canal and tympanic membrane, excluding the removal of the incus in SH coupler stimulation. Reflecting beads for LDV measurements were placed on the stapes footplate and, if insufficiently visible, on the posterior crus.

2.2. Stimulation and measurement

All specimens were first acoustically stimulated to determine the middle ear transfer function and to verify the fulfillment of the ASTM standard F2504-05 criteria (ASTM, 2005). A special version of the FMT (VORP 503) was used with a cable connection for direct electrical stimulation in all experiments. The integrity of the transducer was confirmed at the beginning and the end of the study. For forward

stimulation, a standard stimulation level of 150 mV_{rms} was set, for the reverse stimulation the FMT was driven with 100 mV_p.

Acoustic and electrical stimulation contained a sequence of 50 logarithmically distributed pure tones between 100 and 8'000 Hz in Basel and 23 logarithmically distributed pure tones between 100 and 10'000 Hz in Hannover. We reduced the Basel data with spectral binning to match similar frequencies for better compatibility of the results (see Section 3.2).

2.3. Experimental protocol

For forward stimulation, the incus couplers (SP and LP coupler) and the SH coupler were connected sequentially to the same specimen. LDV measurements were recorded at the stapes and at the RW. Between every change of coupling modality, an acoustic measurement was performed to assure the integrity of the temporal bone (Graf et al., 2024). For the RW stimulation measurements, first an SP coupler was mounted, and the stapes velocity in response to actuator stimulation was measured with LDV in the same manner (Stauske et al. 2025, to be published). Subsequently, cochleostomies of 0.4 mm diameter to *scala vestibuli* and *scala tympani* were drilled and calibrated fiber-optic pressure sensors with a diameter of 310 μm (FOP-M260, Veloce 50, FISO Technologies, Canada) were inserted and glued into both *scala vestibuli* and *scala tympani* similar to Grossöhmichen, 2017 (Grossöhmichen et al., 2017). Cochleostomies and probe insertions were done submerged under saline to prevent cochlear leakage and an acoustical stimulation was repeated after insertion to confirm ASTM compliance. From pressures measured in *scala vestibuli* and *scala tympani* the intracochlear pressure difference (ICPD) was calculated as the vector difference.

The FMT was then attached to a micromanipulator and held against the round window using a rod with controlled static force of 15 Nm. For the RW coupler, a cylindrical piece of silicone was glued between the rod and the FMT (2 × 2 mm, Shore A 40 hardness) to allow for vibration of the FMT. In case of the HC coupler (Research RW-Precision Coupler) the integrated spring was used and fixed to the holding rod. Both the intracochlear pressure difference and the FMT velocity were measured in reverse stimulation experiments (Fig. 1).

2.4. Correction for comparison and for reverse stimulation

The LDV beam was aimed as close as possible to the stapes footplate

Fig. 1. Illustration of all four coupling sites compared in the present study. Forward stimulation: stapes head (SH), long process (LP), short process (SP). Reverse stimulation: round window (RW, HC). SP and LP coupler are used with intact ossicular chain for sensorineural hearing loss. RW and SH are used for conductive and mixed hearing loss. PST: pressure sensor in *scala tympani*. PSV: pressure sensor in *scala vestibuli*. LDV: beam of the laser Doppler vibrometer.

normal direction, the estimated average angle of incidence was 15–45° to the footplate normal. For this analysis, we did not apply the angle correction for the data of both labs, since the same method was used and comparisons between couplers on the same specimen were sought in each case. All velocity and pressure measurements were calculated to an equivalent reference input level of 1 V_p . Both centers performed the same stapes LDV measurement for a standard SP coupler.

To ensure that couplers measured at different institutions are quantitatively comparable, both laboratories performed and compared the same measurement: electromechanical stimulation with an FMT on the SP coupler, velocity measured with LDV on the stapes. The remaining difference was accounted for as a correction factor in the case of direct comparisons between couplers measured at different institutions (SH vs. RW coupler, Section 3.4).

Stieger, 2013 (Stieger et al., 2013) showed that the velocity of the stapes (V_{St}) is a reliable measure of cochlear input during forward stimulation, but not during reverse stimulation. While forward stimulation shows a good correlation between V_{St} and the ICDP across the cochlear partition - with pressure sensors in each *scala vestibuli* and *scala tympani* - reverse stimulation introduces additional fluid leakage through a "third window", probably the cochlear aqueduct, that disrupts this relationship. This leakage flow, especially prominent at frequencies below 1 kHz and varying between ears, causes deviations in stapes velocity V_{St} that no longer accurately represent the true input to the cochlea during reverse stimulation. Therefore, V_{St} measurements need an average correction factor to improve accuracy when assessing cochlear input in reverse stimulation scenarios.

To calculate this correction factor, the V_{St} was measured using LDV and the ICPD in the same 10 temporal bones, at the same stimulation level, using forward (SP coupler) and reverse stimulation (RW coupler). When the ratio between ICPD and V_{St} is plotted for both forward and reverse stimulation, the difference indicates the correction factor. This correction factor may serve in reverse stimulation to account for the underestimation and to compare the actual level to forward stimulation (see Section 3.4).

2.5. Statistical analysis

We used GraphPad Prism® (version 10.4.1, GraphPad Software, Boston, MA, USA) for statistical analysis. Mann-Whitney tests were performed to compare normalized stapes velocities between both centers, and Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were performed to detect significant differences between forward and reverse stimulation in the same temporal bones.

3. Results

3.1. All couplers, stapes motion based (overview)

Fig. 2 shows the transfer function based on a stapes LDV measurement of all couplers investigated. Among the couplers for forward stimulation, the response magnitude for the SH coupler is 8.3 dB (SD 4.5 dB) higher than for the LP coupler averaged between 100 and 8'000 Hz. The response magnitude for the SH coupler is 3.2 dB higher (SD 3.4 dB) than for the SP coupler. The difference between the two reverse stimulation couplers is 1.6 dB (SD 14 dB) between 125 and 10'000 Hz. Without further correction of the velocity data measured at the stapes, the difference between the SP coupler and the RW coupler between 125 and 8'000 Hz would be 20.3 dB (SD 11 dB) according to the LDV measurements.

3.2. Stapes velocity measurement for SP couplers in both centers

The LDV measurements of stapes velocity for the SP coupler experiments at of both centers are plotted in Fig. 3. The magnitudes differ by an average of 6.6 dB between 1500 Hz and 5000 Hz; the difference for

Fig. 2. Magnitude of the transfer function stapes velocity / input voltage, Normalized actuator evoked stapes velocity of all couplers involved (uncorrected). SH: stapes head, SP: short process, LP: long process, RW: round window, HC: Hannover coupler. Shaded area of corresponding color depicts the 95 % confidence interval.

Fig. 3. Comparison of actuator evoked normalized stapes velocity according to the LDV measurements for SP coupling in both centers on $n = 10$ temporal bones each. Significant differences: marked with a gray bar on x-axis ($p < 0.05$; Mann-Whitney test). Shaded area of corresponding color depicts the 95 % confidence intervals.

the entire frequency range from 100 Hz to 8'000 Hz was 1.8 dB. This difference between the same measurement at different institutions was taken into account in the case of the comparison of two couplers measured at different institutions (see Section 3.4).

3.3. Correction for reverse stimulation

To calculate the correction to account for the differences in reverse stimulation for LDV stapes velocity measurements in the case of reverse stimulation, (Fig. 4, left plot) we used the ratio between stapes velocity (V_{St}) and the ICPD (ΔP). Both were normalized to 1 V_p input level. In forward stimulation, the averaged ratio remains approximately constant across the entire frequency range. The difference to the averaged reverse stimulation (Fig. 4, right plot) is most prominent at low frequencies and continuously decreasing towards higher frequencies. It measures 22.4 dB (SD 18 dB) between 125–250 Hz, 7.9 dB (SD 12 dB) between 300–800 Hz, and 4.8 dB (SD 17 dB) above 1'000 Hz. For comparison, the results of the same experimental setup with a different RW stimulator from (Stieger et al., 2013) are plotted, with differences of approximately 12 dB at 125–250 Hz, 7 dB between 300–800 Hz, and 3 dB above 1'000 Hz.

LDV vs. ICPD at reverse (RW) and forward (SP) stimulation

Correction for Stapes LDV at reverse stimulation

Fig. 4. *Left plot:* Ratio between Stapes LDV velocity and intracochlear pressure difference (ICPD) for forward and reverse stimulation at the same stimulation level. VSt: Stapes velocity (LDV), ΔP: Difference between scala vestibuli and scala tympani pressure, FW: forward stimulation, Rev: reverse stimulation, SP: SP-coupler, RW: RW-coupler. Bold lines: averaged data, thin lines: individual data. *Right plot:* Difference between the LDV vs. ICPD ratio, serves as a correction factor for stapes velocity loss at reverse stimulation. Blue line: averaged data current study, gray area: standard deviation, black line: averaged data from Stieger et al. 2013.

3.4. Forward versus reverse stimulation

In order to perform a direct comparison between forward and reverse stimulation using the correction factor for LDV signal loss during reverse stimulation calculated above, this was included into a ratio between SP coupler and RW coupler (Fig. 5, left plot), as all measurements for these are available for the same specimen. This shows a difference for the RW coupler of -15.4 dB (SD 12 dB) in frequencies <2'000 Hz, -6.8 dB (SD 10 dB) at 2'000–8'000 Hz, and -18.2 dB (SD 13 dB) in the frequency range between 200–1600 Hz. Across the entire frequency range of 125–8'000 Hz, the RW coupler is 11.7 dB (SD 11 dB) lower than the SP coupler. A Wilcoxon signed-rank test showed significant differences between 250–1'600 Hz, 3'000–4'000 Hz, and at 6'000 Hz.

To compare the two options for an altered ossicular chain (SH

coupler vs. RW coupler) in a mixed hearing loss situation, the difference between the two institutions (Fig. 3) must be taken into account in addition to the correction described. This comparison is shown in Fig. 5, right plot.

Overall, this results in a considerably better performance of forward stimulation of 15.6 dB (SD 12 dB) in the frequency range of 125–8'000 Hz. This is particularly evident in the range below 2'000 Hz, where it is 22.1 dB (SD 11 dB) at average. At 2000 Hz and above, the average difference is 6.8 dB (SD 11 dB). The largest difference was 25.4 dB (SD 13 dB) at 200–1'600 Hz. A Mann-Whitney test showed significant differences between 200–1'600 Hz and 5'000–6'350 Hz.

RW vs. SP (corrected)

Reverse (RW) vs. forward (SH) +/- correction

Fig. 5. *Left plot:* Stapes LDV difference between forward stimulation with SP coupling and reverse stimulation with RW coupling, reverse stimulation corrected for stapes magnitude loss (see Fig. 4). Normalized to the SP coupler (black bold line). Orange line: mean value, thin black lines individual specimens (n = 10), gray shaded area: standard deviation. Gray bars on x-axis: significant differences (p < 0.05, Wilcoxon signed-rank test) *Right plot:* Stapes LDV difference between forward and reverse stimulation for mixed hearing loss couplers: SH coupler vs. RW coupler. Both curves include the correction for inter-institutional differences (Fig. 3). Orange line: comparison corrected for reverse stimulation stapes magnitude loss. Gray bars on x-axis: significant differences (p < 0.05, Mann-Whitney test). Gray shaded area: standard deviation. Dashed line: before correction for reverse stimulation.

4. Discussion

The study summarizes an overview of the performance of all common Vibrant Soundbridge couplers. It further intends to estimate an adequate correction factor for reverse stimulation to account for errors in stapes velocity measurement results by LDV to enable direct comparison. Small differences between the measurement centers in the frequency range, stimulation levels, and magnitudes of the LDV measurements in the mid-frequency range were identified and adjusted. Overall, the results show that reverse stimulation is not substantially worse than forward stimulation. This is noTable finding, because in some surgeries, this is the only option available intraoperatively. On the other hand, a loss of 6.8–25.4 dB due to reverse coupling is a gain loss that should be taken into consideration in indications. Much of this seems to be due to the concept itself, as the RW coupling has been optimized with a great deal of effort, but still does not come close to matching the performance of the forward couplings (HC Coupler, Fig. 2). The reasons for this probably lies not only in greater variability in surgical coupling (Arnold et al., 2010), but in generally less efficient vibration transmission per se. If the FMT as a whole is connected to a mobile ossicle, the impedance will be lower than if the sound is transmitted to a thin membrane with a (at least largely) static counterpart on the other side.

The loss of magnitude at the stapes in reverse stimulation in humans due to a suspected third window, as opposed to, for example, in chinchilla (Tollin et al., 2023), is known. Although (Stieger et al., 2013) used a piezoelectric actuator and an FMT with round tip for reverse stimulation, our comparison of forward and reverse FMT stimulation shows that the correction factor can be reproduced relatively well, albeit it is slightly higher <250 Hz. In both studies, the variability of individual results is high.

It should be noted that the incus was not removed when calculating the correction factor for reverse stimulation. This does not correspond to surgical reality, as the normal ossicular chain would no longer be present in many cases. There is probably no relevant additional attenuation of the stapes velocity greater than a few dB due to the presence of the incus, as indicated by Stauske et al. (Stauske, 2025, to be published). Any effects of the case of a tympanosclerotic fixed stapes footplate in reverse coupling were not evaluated. It must also be mentioned that a single-point LDV measurement of the stapes velocity may also slightly overestimate velocity responses during forward stimulation with an SH coupler due to a change in axis rotation caused by stimulation with an angled FMT. While the difference across the entire frequency range between SH and LP couplers measured at the stapes was 8.3 dB, it is only 3.4 dB (± 8.1) when measured at the RW (Graf et al., 2024).

5. Conclusion

Based on our preclinical measurements, we conclude that forward cochlear stimulation with an SH coupler for mixed hearing loss is 7–25 dB and with an SP coupler 7–18 dB superior to the performance of an RW coupling. The effective output range of the SH coupler is similar to that of incus couplers for pure sensorineural hearing loss. If, during an implantation operation for mixed hearing loss, coupling to the stapes can be performed instead of reverse coupling, a performance reserve can be assumed. Clinical audiological evaluations will be required in the future to confirm the actual indication range.

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Ethical approval

The use of human temporal bones was approved by the local ethics commission (Basel EKNZ BASEC 2016-00599 and Hannover

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Lukas Graf: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **David Stauske:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Mohammad Ghoncheh:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Andreas Arnold:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Hamidreza Mojallal:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Christof Stieger:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Hannes Maier:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Funding to the project, see declaration title page reports financial support was provided by MED-EL Electromedical Equipment. David Stauske and Hamidreza Mojallal reports a relationship with MED-EL Electromedical Equipment that includes: employment. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

References

- Arnold, A., Stieger, C., Candreia, C., Pffiffer, F., Kompis, M., 2010. Factors improving the vibration transfer of the floating mass transducer at the round window. *Otol. Neurotol.* 31, 122–128.
- ASTM 2005. International F2504-05: standard practice for describing system output of ImplanTable middle ear hearing devices.
- Busch, S., Lenarz, T., Maier, H., 2017. Comparison of alternative coupling methods of the vibrant soundbridge floating mass transducer. *Audiol. Neurotol.* 21, 347–355.
- Colletti, V., Soli, S.D., Carner, M., Colletti, L., 2006. Treatment of mixed hearing losses via implantation of a vibratory transducer on the round window: tratamiento de hipoacusias mixtas con un transductor vibratorio en la ventana redonda. *Int. J. Audiol.* 45, 600–608.
- Dietz, T.G., Ball, G.R., Katz, B.H., 1997. Partially implanTable vibrating ossicular prosthesis. In: *Proceedings of International Solid State Sensors and Actuators Conference (Transducers' 97)*. IEEE, pp. 433–436.
- Graf, L., Lochner, J., Mojallal, H., Arnold, A., Honegger, F., Stieger, C., 2023. Comparison between incus short process and long process coupling of the vibrant Soundbridge in human temporal bones. *Int. J. Audiol.* 62, 192–198.
- Graf, L., Lochner, J., Mojallal, H., Arnold, A., Honegger, F., Stieger, C., 2024. Experimental quantification of the vibrant soundbridge stapes head (SH-) coupler in human cadaveric temporal bones: evaluation of a re-designed coupler for severe mixed hearing loss. *Int. J. Audiol.* 1–7.
- Grossöhlichen, M., Salcher, R., Lenarz, T., Maier, H., 2017. Measurement of intracochlear pressure differences in human temporal bones using an off-the-shelf pressure sensor. *Biomedical Technology: Modeling, Experiments and Simulation*. Springer.
- Huber, A.M., Ball, G.R., Veraguth, D., Dillier, N., Bodmer, D., Sequeira, D., 2006. A new implanTable middle ear hearing device for mixed hearing loss: a feasibility study in human temporal bones. *Otol. Neurotol.* 27, 1104–1109.
- Hüttenbrink, K.B., Beutner, D., Bornitz, M., Luers, J.C., Zahnert, T., 2011. Clip vibroplasty: experimental evaluation and first clinical results. *Otol. Neurotol.* 32, 650–653.
- Schraven, S.P., Dalhoff, E., Wildenstein, D., Hagen, R., Gummer, A.W., Mlynski, R., 2014. Alternative fixation of an active middle ear implant at the short incus process. *Audiol. Neurotol.* 19, 1–11.
- Schraven, S.P., Gromann, W., Rak, K., Shehata-Dieler, W., Hagen, R., Mlynski, R., 2016. Long-term stability of the active middle-ear implant with floating-mass transducer technology: a single-center study. *Otol. Neurotol.* 37, 252–266.
- Spiegel, J.L., Kutsch, L., Jakob, M., Weiss, B.G., Canis, M., Ihler, F., 2020. Long-term stability and functional outcome of an active middle ear implant regarding different coupling sites. *Otol. Neurotol.* 41, 60–67.

- Stieger, C., Rosowski, J.J., Nakajima, H.H., 2013. Comparison of forward (ear-canal) and reverse (round-window) sound stimulation of the cochlea. *Hear. Res.* 301, 105–114.
- Tollin, D.J., Koka, K., Peacock, J., 2023. Using stapes velocity to estimate the efficacy of mechanical stimulation of the round window with an active middle ear implant. *Otol. Neurotol.* 44, e311–e318.
- Warnholtz, B., Schär, M., Cuny, P., Sonntag, K., Beutner, D., Dobrev, I., Rösli, C., Sim, J. H., 2021. A new stapes-head coupler for the Vibrant Soundbridge system. *Audiol. Neurotol.* 26, 287–294.